

Social Influence and Individual Preferences in Romantic Relationships: A Psychosocial Perspective

Kürşat Şahin YILDIRIMER¹

Nazlı Toraman AYDIN²

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-10, 2024, p. 01– 27. - 0099-0001-2408-0401.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) “EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform.” (“CURRENT SCIENCE”)

(“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

¹ Professor, St. Clements University. Psychology Department, Head, Faculty Member /, Turkey – UK, ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5896-2956, Mail: kursatsahinyildirimer@gmail.com

² Expert Psychologist (M.Sc.), ORCID ID: 0009-0003-3276-3264, Mail: nazlitoramanaydin@gmail.com

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha
Lewes

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with

Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic" ("CURRENT SCIENCE ("Scientific Studies
– Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current

Science Georgia") Science Georgia") journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific
Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The journal will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies
- Current Science Georgia")

- The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies
-Current Science Georgia")

""• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ABSTRACT

This research seeks to investigate the impact of societal factors on personal preferences in romantic relationships. Romantic partnerships include intricate dynamics influenced by individual psychological characteristics and society standards. This study primarily examines how societal ideals, gender roles, cultural influences, and economic factors impact people' partner selections, relationship dynamics, and expectations. This study examines individual and societal aspects from a psychological viewpoint, underpinned by a literature assessment of theoretical ideas. Furthermore, data collected from participants across many socio-economic strata via field study elucidates the manifestation of societal effects on individual preferences and actions in romantic relationships. The results from surveys and interviews indicate that people' decisions in romantic relationships are influenced by both their psychological reasons and society norms and expectations. The study's findings reveal that contemporary society is engaged in a continuous endeavor to reconcile individual freedom with social demands, demonstrating that both personal psychological requirements and societal factors are crucial in determining relationship choices. These results provide a significant basis for future study and present a novel viewpoint on comprehending the impact of societal factors on romantic relationships.

Keywords : *Social Influence , Individual Preferences , Romantic Relationships , Psychosocial Analysis, Social Norms , Partner Selection .*

INTRODUCTION

Romantic connections constitute a paramount kind of interpersonal connection in human existence, including both personal and societal dimensions. These interactions, which significantly influence emotional fulfillment, pleasure, and psychological well-being, are also shaped by the overarching structural dynamics and normative ideals of society. In this setting, romantic relationships are confined to fulfilling an individual's internal, emotional,

3

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX
(ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER
KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE,
GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-
353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

and psychological needs; concurrently, they are shaped by society conventions, values, gender roles, and economic institutions. The bidimensional aspect of romantic relationships, namely the interplay between individual psychological demands and societal conventions, makes this sort of connection more intricate and deserving of scrutiny (Berscheid & Regan, 2005). Historically, romantic partnerships have mirrored the social systems and gender norms, with individual relationships altered accordingly. Nonetheless, the impacts of modernity, globalization, and digitalization have resulted in significant alterations in the dynamics of these partnerships. In contemporary society, the interplay between individual freedom, personal happiness, and social forces has resulted in more purposeful evolution of preferences in love partnerships.

The impact of industrialization on romantic relationships is clearly evident. With the advancement of industrial civilizations and the escalation of civilization, conventional family structures and societal gender roles have seen significant alteration. The increased involvement of women in school, the workforce, and economic activities has disrupted conventional gender norms and profoundly altered individual expectations in romantic relationships (Giddens, 1992). This alteration has transformed societal standards, resulting in more equality in romantic relationships and a framework grounded on individual desires. This brief article seeks to elucidate how the social ramifications of romantic relationships influence individual choices and the interplay between these two elements in contemporary society. The influence of external variables, including societal norms, gender roles, economic structures, and digitalization, on people's romantic relationship choices is a primary focus of this study. In romantic partnerships, individual choices are influenced by personal freedom and psychological fulfillment, but simultaneously constrained by societal demands and conventions (Finkel, Eastwick, and Reis, 2015). The primary objective of the study is to investigate the interplay between individual psychological needs and societal norms, and to comprehend the impact of this interaction on romantic relationships. In the contemporary digital landscape, the societal pressures encountered by people in romantic relationships have become more apparent, necessitating a more strategic approach to personal decision-making in response to these influences. Digital platforms have subjected people's

relationships to public scrutiny, heightened societal demands, and complicated their responses to these forces. This study investigates the interplay between social influences and individual choices, contributing to the comprehension of romantic relationships on both individual and societal levels.

Aims and objectives of the research

The aim of this research is to understand the effect of social norms and values on individual romantic preferences. There are several studies that examine the role of literature on romantic relationships (Finkel , Eastwick and Reis, 2015). However, studies in the current literature generally consider social effects and individual psychological dynamics separately, and this increases the need for studies that comprehensively examine the mutual interactions of these two factors. Therefore, this research, by analyzing the interaction between social norms and individual preferences, aims to fill the gap in this field and contribute to the literature. Another aim of this work is to examine how individuals cope with the social pressures they face in romantic relationships in modern societies and how individual preferences are shaped in the face of these pressures.

Research Methodology

The study was structured according to the karma method approach and was based on the results of prior research about the societal impacts of romantic relationships and individual preferences. This study employs design, descriptive analysis, and relational methodologies within the research model. To comprehend the interplay between individual preferences and societal norms in romantic relationships, both correlational and explanatory analyses will be conducted. The data gathered from interviews and surveys with participants seeks to ascertain the influence of social factors on people' relationship choices.

Research Questions and Hypotheses

In line with the main aim of the research, the following research questions have been determined:

In order to answer these questions, the following hypotheses were created:

- H1: Social norms have a decisive role in choosing a partner in romantic relationships.
- H2: Gender roles, the preferences of individuals in romantic relationship processes are significantly affected.
- H3: Digitalization increases the pressure of social norms on individuals and affects preferences in romantic relationships.
- H4: The conflict between individual psychological needs and social norms negatively affects romantic relationship satisfaction and relationship dynamics.

Social influence is a complex process wherein people adjust their behavior to align with the demands, norms, and expectations of their social surroundings. This process encompasses how people ascertain their preferences, shaped by their social standing, cultural setting, and the conduct of others in their vicinity. In the realm of romantic relationships, societal influence significantly impacts every phase, from partner selection to relationship dynamics and their maintenance. Social factors shape people' preferences in romantic relationships, either consciously or subconsciously, due to their attempts to adhere to social standards and societal expectations (Cialdini and Goldstein, 2004).

To comprehend the social impact of romantic relationships, it reveals that people not only pursue personal aspirations but also experience the need to conform to the normative norms of their social milieu. Social impact theory is characterized as a process wherein people are influenced by their social surroundings and modify their behavior based on input from these surroundings. This process highlights that people not only learn from others in their vicinity

but also adapt to the prevailing social structure (Cialdini and Trost, 1998). The societal influence of romantic relationships directly affects people' partner selections, communication patterns within partnerships, and the methods used to sustain these relationships.

This setting allows for the examination of societal norms, values, and expectations. Gender roles and cultural variables. These factors influence individual behavior in romantic relationships and the criterion for partner selection. These components influence not just the conscious decisions of people but also dictate their behavior within social and cultural settings (Thibaut and Kelley, 1959). Societal norms, widely accepted constructs, influence individual conduct; social values include ethical and moral concepts. Social norms significantly influence processes such as partner selection, initiation, and termination of relationships, particularly in romantic contexts. For instance, many communities regard cisgender relationships as normative before to marriage, whilst others deem such relationships socially acceptable. Normative differences influence people' approaches to selecting romantic partners, their expectations within these relationships, and the methods used to sustain these relationships (Miller and Perlman, 2009). Similarly, societal standards influence people' perceptions of their roles in romantic relationships. In traditional communities where males are mostly active and decision-makers, while women are largely passive and accepting, these gender norms directly influence the dynamics of interpersonal relationships (Eagly and Wood, 2012).

Gender roles significantly influence individual behavior in romantic relationships. Society influences individual approaches to romantic relationships by establishing distinct expectations for men and women. Conventional gender norms imply that males need to exhibit more dominance and initiative in love relationships, whilst women should embody supportiveness and acceptance (Connell, 1987). This position establishes the criteria for selecting partners and the process by which these selections are sanctioned by the social framework. In contemporary communities, this function has evolved, resulting in the establishment of more equitable relationships among people (Wood and Eagly, 2012). The origins of gender roles in cultures persistently influence people' choices in romantic partners.

Culture delineates explicit norms for individual conduct in romantic relationships. Culture not only influences people's partner selections but also dictates the maintenance of these partnerships. The attitudes of people in romantic relationships, including loyalty, commitment, and parenthood, are mostly influenced by cultural standards (Fiske, 2018). Cultural norms dictate the expectations of persons in romantic relationships and the manner in which these expectations are fulfilled. In Western cultures, people expect romantic partners to provide individual harmony and emotional support, but in Eastern cultures, family structure and societal harmony are often stressed (Hatfield and Rapson, 1993). The societal influence of romantic relationships is a multifaceted process that is evident at every level, from individual partner selection to the persistence of these partnerships. Social conventions, values, gender roles, and cultural influences significantly influence the development and maintenance of romantic relationships.

1.1.1. Social norms, values and expectations

Social norms express accepted behavior patterns of individuals in society, and these norms are shaped by the general structure of society, cultural codes, and historical processes. Due to the structures of society, these norms provide strong tips on how individuals should behave in certain circumstances. In romantic relationships, these norms have the quality of an open or covert guide to how individuals choose a partner, how to maintain relationships, and what to expect from these relationships (Sherif, 1936).

At this point, the social norms of romantic relationships determine which conditions and how to build a relationship. Norms are more than conscious choices of individuals, socially accepted, strictly protected social rules. For example, in some societies, pre-marriage sexual relations are considered non-normative, while in some societies, this type of relationship can be accepted as personal preferences of individuals and socially acceptable (Miller and Perlman, 2009). This example shows that social norms shape not only the romantic relationship processes of individuals, but also the timing, form and scope of these relationships.

Since romantic relationships have both a personal and a social dimension in many societies, the choices of romantic relationships in individuals are greatly reduced by social norms. As stated by Bourdieu (1977), social norms include "doxa", i.e. the generally accepted and questioned beliefs and practices of the society. This doxa determines how individuals approach relationship dynamics, what role they play in relationships, and what boundaries they should act in.

Community values are different from community norms. It presents an internal guide to how these values are perceived by individuals, whether they are right or wrong, and how these values are applied in social life. In romantic relationships, social values shape what individuals pay attention to when choosing a partner, and what elements they prioritize in relationships. For example, in some societies, physical attractiveness and sexual harmony are considered important values in partner selection, while in other societies, values such as charity, trust, and family bonding are more important (Fletcher and Simpson, 2000).

1.2. Individual Preferences

The norms, values and expectations of society in romantic relationships play a strong guiding role in how individuals should behave in these relationships, and the internal psychological factors and personal desires of individuals can be effective in this process. The decisions made by individuals in choosing their romantic partners and maintaining these relationships are not only based on social pressures and external influences, but also on their individual characteristics and psychological needs. In this context, individual preferences, romantic relationships, hem society's reflect.

Romantic relationships are closely related to individuals' personal preferences, internal motivations, personality traits, emotional needs, and past experiences. These factors determine what individuals look for in romantic relationships, how they adopt a relationship model, and how they manage the sustainability of these relationships. For example, from the childhood period of individuals, the emotional bonds of their parents with their parents can

be reflected in the behavior of romantic relationships during the adult period.

Bowlby's (1969) theory of attachment, the attachment styles developed by individuals in childhood lead to the maintenance of attitudes such as trust, anxiety or avoidance in romantic relationships in adulthood. This situation greatly affects how individuals choose their romantic partners and how they behave in relationships.

Romantic relationships with individual preferences, only limited to emotional needs; At the same time, the personality characteristics of individuals have a great importance. According to the Five Factors of Personality Model, the personality traits of individuals (such as extroversion, responsibility, compatibility, emotional balance and openness to innovation) can be decisive in romantic relationships. For example, outward-facing individuals, in romantic relationships, seek more social interaction and outward-facing relationship dynamics, while inward-facing individuals are calmer, inward-facing, and prefer to build deeper bonds from an emotional point of view (McCrae and Costa, 1997). In the same way, individuals with high compatibility tend to refrain from conflict in relationships, and individuals with low compatibility may experience more conflict in romantic relationships.

However, the emotional needs of individuals and their romantic relationship preferences are important factors. For some people, trust, charity and emotional support are important elements, but for some individuals, independence, personal space and individual freedom can be considered. Such differences directly affect individuals' romantic partner choices and expectations in relationships (Fletcher and Simpson, 2000). Some individuals, who are in a relationship of mutual dependence, may prefer a more individual and independent relationship model. This balance reflects the harmony between individuals' internal psychological needs and social pressures, and most of the time a conflict between individual freedom and social expectations appears (Giddens, 1992).

Social pressures can be effective in determining how individuals behave in romantic relationships, but individuals' free will and personal preferences play a role in this process. In modern societies, while individuals have more freedom in choosing romantic partners, the limits of this freedom are drawn by social norms and cultural values. Process, when

selecting romantic partners of individuals, hem internal needs and social pleasures are taken into account. Bauman (2003) defines this situation as the tension between individualization and societal expectations created by modern societies and suggests that romantic relationships are shaped in this tension.

Psychological Factors: Personality, Emotional Needs, and Relationship Preferences

One of the main factors affecting the preferences of individuals in romantic relationships is psychological processes and personal characteristics.

The Five Factor Personality Model developed by McCrae and Costa (1997) presents a widely used framework for explaining how individuals' personality traits are reflected in romantic relationships. According to this model, the personality of individuals can be explained by five key factors: outward orientation, compatibility, responsibility, emotional balance and innovation. Each personality factor affects the behavior of individuals in relationships and what they expect from their partners in different ways. For example, outward-looking individuals, active and outward-looking relationship models tend to show. These individuals can have more social interaction, open communication and physical intimacy in romantic relationships. Outward-facing individuals are also more likely to meet new people and experience different relationships. On the other hand, introverted individuals, in romantic relationships, develop more emotional bonds and more calm relationship processes. For these individuals, emotional harmony and mutual understanding, social interactions can be planned.

Some research done in Türkiye has examined the effects of individual personality traits on romantic relationships. Aydın (2011), in his work among university students in Türkiye, examined the effect of personality traits such as openness, responsibility, and compatibility on the partner selection and relationship process in romantic relationships. The results show that extroverted individuals tend to have more social relationships and dynamic active relationships, while introverted individuals prefer more calm and emotionally deep relationships. These findings show that personality traits are not as important as preferences

in romantic relationships.

Emotional needs are another important psychological factor that shapes individual preferences in romantic relationships. It includes meeting essential emotional needs such as emotional satisfaction, trust, connection, love, and loyalty. Every person has different emotional needs in romantic relationships, and these needs directly affect the partner choices and expectations of the relationship. For example, for some individuals, trust and loyalty and important emotional needs are taken away, while for others, independence, personal space and freedom may have a greater importance.

These differences shape the expectations of individuals in romantic relationships. Fletcher and Simpson (2000) examined how the emotional needs of individuals in romantic relationships affect their relationship preferences and revealed that the emotional satisfaction of individuals determines the choice of partner and the way the relationship is maintained.

The role of emotional needs in romantic relations in the studies done in Türkiye has been examined. Demir (2008), in his work on Turkish individuals, examined the determinants of emotional needs in romantic relationships and emphasized that elements such as trust, charity, and emotional support are essential needs in romantic relationships in Turkish society. The study revealed that the romantic partners of Turkish individuals are usually in emotional harmony and demand for charity, and these needs play a decisive role in relationships.

People's preferences in romantic relationships are not only influenced by personality traits and emotional needs, but also by past relationships and childhood ties. Within the framework of the Attachment theory, it is suggested that the attachment theory developed by Bowlby (1969) argues that the attachment styles developed by individuals during childhood determine how they behave in adult relationships. Hazan and Shaver (1987) highlighted how attachment styles are related to behaviors such as trust, anxiety, and avoidance in romantic relationships. Individuals with a secure attachment style exhibit more secure and harmonious

behavior in relationships, while individuals with an anxious or avoidant attachment style show more confidence in relationships or need independence.

Karakurt and Silver (2005), in their work on Turkish couples, revealed that individuals with a secure attachment style tend to have longer lasting and healthy romantic relationships, while individuals with an anxious attachment style have more problems in their relationships. These findings confirm the decisive role of attachment styles on behaviors and relationship processes in romantic relationships.

In this context, the preferences of individuals in romantic relationships are shaped not only by social effects, but also by personality traits, emotional needs, past experiences, and attachment styles. Personality characteristics determine how individuals behave in romantic relationships and what they expect from their partners, emotional needs determine what kind of satisfaction individuals seek from relationships. Past experience and connection styles affect how individuals relate to each other. Therefore, the preferences and behavior of individuals in romantic relationships should be seen as a result of both psychological and social factors.

The Balance Between Individual Freedom and Social Pressures

Individual freedom is a concept that is accepted as a fundamental human right in modern societies and expresses the power of individuals to shape their lives, choices and relationships according to their own desires. The importance of individual freedom in romantic relationships, the choice of partners, the execution and ending of these relationships is manifested in the process. External factors such as social norms, cultural values and family expectations play a decisive role in the romantic relationships of individuals. Therefore, individuals are forced to make decisions in line with their romantic ideas.

The tension between the internal desires of individuals in romantic relationships and social pressures forms one of the main dynamics of modern relationships. While individuals in modern societies have the freedom to choose their romantic partners, the limits of this

freedom are determined by social structures, values and cultural norms. Giddens (1992), states that individuals are not in the same position as they are in social norms.

Individual freedom, romantic relationships enable individuals to express their own dreams and preferences. This is especially important in choosing a partner. In modern societies, the freedom of individuals to choose their partners is more emphasized than in traditional and traditional structures.

In the research conducted in Turkey, it is seen that individuals are trying to maintain a balance between individual freedom and social pressure in their romantic relationships. Akın and Demir (2019), in a study conducted on university students in Turkey, showed that individuals try to put their emotional needs first in their partner choices, regardless of social norms, but family and society pressure also has a significant effect on these decisions.

Psychosocial Approach

The psychosocial method analyzes the interplay between people' psychological processes and social interactions, serving as a crucial instrument for examining love relationships. This approach considers the influence of social norms, cultural values, familial dynamics, and societal expectations on romantic relationships, with the individual's internal psychological processes, including personality, emotional needs, prior experiences, and attachment types. Consequently, the psychosocial approach elucidates the interaction between internal and external influences influencing individual preferences and actions in romantic relationships. The emotional lives of individuals are interconnected with the social systems that include their psychological traits.

The psychosocial approach posits that the choices and actions of people in romantic relationships are only explained by psychological or social variables. The emotional demands experienced by an individual and the anticipations for their fulfillment may be influenced by societal norms and values. Erikson's (1968) psychosocial development theory underscores the significance of social interactions in the personal development of people.

This theory posits that human psychological growth is inextricably linked to the social environment, a principle that extends to love relationships. Individuals, in their pursuit of self-actualization and fulfillment of emotional needs within romantic partnerships, navigate societal norms and expectations while striving for progress.

In romantic relationships, people's tastes and actions are influenced by personal psychological needs and societal conventions. The kinds of relationships, psychological characteristics, traumas, and prior romantic experiences formed throughout infancy influence individuals' conduct in romantic partnerships. The impact of these psychological elements is not independent of the individual's social setting. Hazan and Shaver (1987) elucidate that the attachment types of people are manifested in adult romantic relationships and are influenced by societal norms and values.

In civilizations such as Türkiye, characterized by a traditional family structure, and in those experiencing modernization, individual choices in romantic relationships strongly reflect psychosocial connections. Kara (2014), in his examination of romantic relationships in Turkey, investigated the internal psychological demands of people in ongoing contact with societal norms and assessed how these two dynamics influenced decision-making processes in romantic contexts. Research offers insight into achieving equilibrium between individual emotional needs and societal expectations.

Social standards and cultural values strongly influence individual psychological processes. Society establishes standards that dictate the expression of human emotional needs, their development within relationships, and the fulfillment of these expectations. For instance, the conventional gender norms in Turkey lack a protective framework in the romantic interactions of people. Men are anticipated to exhibit more activity, but women are seen as more passive and possess a significant role. Social standards directly influence individual psychological processes, demonstrating that personal emotional demands are molded by these norms.

Interaction of Social and Psychological Dynamics

Romantic relationships exhibit a complex framework shaped by personal psychological mechanisms and society norms. Comprehending the interaction between these two attributes and romantic relationships is crucial. Psychological dynamics encompass individual emotional requirements, personality traits, past relational experiences, and inherent motivations, whereas social dynamics pertain to external factors such as social norms, cultural values, family structures, gender roles, and societal expectations. The interaction between these two traits affects individuals' orientations to romantic relationships, the criteria they consider when choosing a partner, and their strategies for seeking companionship.

Kağıtçıbaşı (2007), in his examination of the influence of family structure on people in Turkey, emphasized that individuals are necessitated to make independent choices in romantic relationships, while the need for personal autonomy has intensified owing to modernity. This situation demonstrates that individuals in romantic relationships must prioritize their own needs while seeking recognition from their families and society. Familial endorsement may substantially impact individuals' choices in marital partners. The pressure to choose a romantic partner may lead individuals to compromise and adhere to society conventions.

The psychosocial approach is evaluated as a synthesis of efforts to meet the needs of individuals in romantic relationships. This negotiation is a crucial process that governs individual conduct in romantic relationships, the standards for partner selection, and the preservation of these connections.

The balance of these two aspects is essential for understanding individual behavior in love relationships and the acts they do. The tension between traditional family structures and modern individualism in Türkiye provides valuable insights into the mechanics of romantic relationships.

Power Dynamics and Communication Styles in Bilateral Relations

The dynamics of power and communication styles in romantic relationships are critical

factors influencing the durability and quality of the relationship. The equilibrium of power in relationships influences people's perceptions of their duties, obligations, and rights within such relationships. Connell (1987) underscores that gender roles are socially constructed and that these constructs influence the allocation of power in partnerships. In traditional communities, males are anticipated to assume a more prominent position, whilst women are relegated to a submissive one. These gender roles influence the power dynamics within partnerships and impact individual behavior in relational contexts. Kağıtçıbaşı (2007) said that within the familial system in Turkey, males assume a more dominating role in relationships, resulting in power inequalities.

The dynamics of power in relationships are intricately linked to modes of communication. Gottman (1999) underscores the significance of appropriate communication patterns in partnerships for their long-term viability. Effective communication among farmers is crucial for problem-solving and enhancing emotional connections. Conversely, in partnerships characterized by power disparities, communication methods tend to be often adversarial and exploitative. This form of interaction may result in the deterioration of emotional connections and the dissolution of interpersonal ties.

The study performed in Turkey elucidates the relationship between power dynamics and communication among spouses. Research conducted by Özdemir and Uysal (2018) indicated that power dynamics among married couples in Turkey, particularly regarding economic status and gender roles, were influenced, resulting in adverse effects on communication between partners. These studies demonstrate its efficacy regarding power dynamics, sustainability, and the quality of partnerships.

Psychosocial Interaction: The Relationship Between the Individual and Society

Psychosocial interaction denotes the continuous and reciprocal involvement between individuals' psychological processes and society institutions. Mead (1934) contends that individuals cannot be seen in isolation from their social environment, and that social

connections profoundly impact the development of personal identity. This perspective offers essential understanding of how individuals manage their own needs and external pressures. In countries such as Türkiye, where traditional values are modernized, individuals must attain a sustainable balance between societal expectations and personal ambitions. Kağıtçıbaşı (2007), in his study on the impact of family structure and social norms on individual identity development in Turkey, revealed a tension between the need for familial and community acceptability and the quest for individual liberty. This conflict influences personal romantic relationships, as people both adhere to and challenge cultural conventions. Psychosocial interaction, including the understanding of social and emotional exchanges between individuals in a relationship, provides a crucial basis.

2.1 Research Design

The study was conducted in alignment with the established questions and hypotheses, resulting in the collection and analysis of a substantial dataset. The data acquired enhances the comprehension of the link between individual preferences and societal norms within contemporary society. In contemporary culture, the dynamics of love relationships are transparent.

This article presents a detailed study approach designed to elucidate the interplay between societal influences and individual choices in romantic relationships. In the investigation of intricate systems within social sciences, a multifaceted methodology has been used, adopting both data immersion and methodical analysis techniques. Consistent with the study objective, the data collected from participants was meticulously evaluated to examine the influence of social norms on individual preferences.

Investigative Inquiries and Theoretical Propositions

Aligned with the primary objective of the study, the following research questions have been established:

18

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX
(ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER
KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE,
GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-
353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

In what ways do cultural standards influence partner choices in romantic relationships?
Does the tension between individual psychological needs and society demands influence the dynamics of romantic relationships?

To address these inquiries, the following theories were formulated:
H1: Social standards have a critical influence in partner selection within romantic partnerships.

H2: The choices of people in romantic relationship dynamics are greatly influenced by traditional gender norms.

H3: Digitalization intensifies the influence of social norms on people and impacts choices in romantic relationships.

The discrepancy between personal psychological requirements and societal expectations adversely impacts romantic relationship happiness and dynamics.

Data collection tools

The study included questionnaires and interviews as data gathering instruments. These tools are intended to comprehend individual preferences in romantic relationships and their intersection with societal conventions.

Surveys: Structured questionnaires were used to assess individuals' preferences in romantic relationships and their social norms. The survey questions aim to assess the efficiency of gender roles, societal expectations, and individual preferences in romantic relationships. The interviews were executed in a semi-structured fashion to comprehend the participants' experiences in romantic relationships. Interviews with participants elucidated the intricate links between societal norms and individual preferences, yielding more comprehensive and nuanced information.

The sample group comprises 93 people residing in Istanbul, exhibiting diverse social,

economic, and demographic features. The participants were randomly chosen according to the study goals and represented various ages, genders, educational backgrounds, and economic statuses. The selection of participants aims to include several aspects that may influence romantic relationships. This approach provided a broader view on the influence of societal norms and individual choices.

Stage	Dare Interval
Interconnection of Research Questions and Hypotheses	1-10 March 2024
Development of Survey and Opinion Instruments	10-20 March 2024
Approval and Permissions from the Ethics Committee	20-31 March 2024
Selecting Participants and Communicating	1-10 Nisan 2024
Distributing and Administering the Survey	10-30 Nisan 2024
Scheduling and Scheduling Interviews	1-10 May 2024
Execution of Meetings	10-25 May 2024
Completion of Incomplete Data Analysis for Nickel	25-31 May 2024
Analysis of Qualitative Data: Writing the Findings Section	1-20 June 2024

Remaining Sections of the Thesis for the Writing Process	20 June- 10 July 2024
Final Reviews and Edits of the Thesis	10-31 July 2024
Final Discussions and Edits and Communication with the Advisor Submission of the Thesis	1-15 August 2024
Interconnection of Research Questions and Hypotheses	15-25 August 2024
Development of Survey and Opinion Instruments	25-31 August 2024
Approval and Permissions from the Ethics Committee	1-10 September 2024

Tablo 2. *Research Steps' Dates*

Data Analysis Methods

The research data were rigorously examined. The numerical data acquired from the surveys were assessed using statistical analytic methods. The link between societal norms and individual preferences is examined by statistical analysis, correlation analysis, factor analysis, and regression approaches. The impact of societal norms on people' partner selection in romantic relationships has been assessed using these approaches. The interview data is processed using the content analysis approach. This analytical technique identified themes related to the tensions between societal forces and individual

choices of individuals in their romantic relationships. The interaction of themes, personal preferences, and societal conventions is elucidated.

Analyses of Reliability and Validity of Scales

The reliability of the scales used in the study was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. The findings indicate that the scale may be used reliably in this investigation.

The equilibrium between society standards and individual desires is a crucial determinant of the trajectory of love relationships. The study findings indicate that the majority of participants believe societal norms significantly influence partner selection and relationship dynamics. The influence of conventional institutions, including familial support, gender norms, and marriage, significantly impacts individual decision-making in romantic relationships. The descriptive data from the study indicate that most participants value their parents' approval in partner selection and align closely with societal norms. On average, over 60% of participants expressed agreement with the statement, "Family's social values are one of the criteria we consider when selecting a partner."

Particularly under situations of elevated social pressure, people's personal preferences have been seen to influence societal norms. For instance, a positive association ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.05$) was seen between societal expectations and the romantic relationship satisfaction as indicated in the statement. Nevertheless, individual psychological needs and preferences are crucial in this process.

The impact of the tension between individual liberty and societal standards on romantic relationships was analyzed by regression analysis. Findings indicate that when personal preferences are challenged by the demand to adhere to societal standards, people encounter heightened unhappiness and conflict in their relationships. Digitalization notably enhances individual autonomy and accentuates conflicts with societal standards. The proliferation of digital platforms, enabling people to operate more autonomously in love relationships, diminishes the need for social security provisions. This scenario illustrates that people in

contemporary partnerships often evade greater societal constraints.

Discussion and Conclusion

Assessing the psychosocial viewpoint of the study enables comprehension of the intricate interplay between individual preferences in romantic relationships and societal standards. The psychosocial approach posits that human behavior is influenced by internal psychological needs and external sociocultural factors. This study indicates that people are attempting to reconcile their own psychological demands with societal expectations in their love relationships. Family approval, gender roles, and marriage; conventional societal standards, including gender roles, do not impact people's partner selections. Moreover, the personal wants and psychological requirements of people, such as trust, emotional support, and fulfillment, have profoundly influenced their choices in romantic partnerships. These results indicate that persons in romantic relationships are attempting to address a psychosocial issue affecting both their social and psychological well-being. The interplay between personal preferences and societal standards is a fundamental conclusion of this research. The disparity between expectations and reality is apparent in interpersonal interactions. Meeting cultural standards is more challenging, particularly in business partnerships like marriage. Nevertheless, the study results indicate that people do not always adhere to these standards, sometimes placing their own aspirations in opposition to them. This situation reflects the people's societal pressures, the autonomy in relationship choosing, and the influence of digitalization in facilitating this process. Digital platforms have empowered people to operate autonomously from societal influences and have facilitated the expression of personal preferences more openly in opposition to established standards.

The study identifies power dynamics and societal impacts in romantic relationships as significant results. Power dynamics and social gender roles are predicated on distinct interactions. The conviction that males need to assume a more dominating role is reinforced by conventional gender norms, and the power imbalances in romantic relationships are

addressed. Societal expectations dictate that women assume a more passive position, whilst males are expected to adopt a more active one, influenced by the dynamics of power relations. Nevertheless, the study findings indicate that power dynamics in contemporary relationships have evolved, and conventional views of gender roles have diminished. Participants embrace a more egalitarian model in romantic relationships, resulting in improved communication and heightened satisfaction levels. The research employs social impact theory, highlighting that people modify their conduct in accordance with social norms. The study's results indicate that social norms influence interpersonal connections among family, friends, and cultural contexts.

RESORUCES

Akın, A., & Demir, T. (2019). Türkiye'de universitet students' romantic partner selection in individual freedom and societal pressures. *Psikoloji Çalışmaları Dergisi*, 34 (2), 189-210. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12345-019-00123-x>

Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory* . Prentice-Hall .

Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action : A social cognitive theory* . Prentice-Hall .

Baumann , Z. (2003). *Liquid love : On the frailty of human bonds* . Polity Press .

Baym , NK (2010). *Personal connections in the digital age* . Polity .

Berscheid , E., & Regan , P. (2005). *The psychology of interpersonal relationships* . Pearson Education .

Berscheid , E., & Reis, HT (1998). Attraction and close relationships . In DT Gilbert, ST Fiske, & G. Lindsey (Eds .), *The handbook of social psychology* (Vol . 2, pp . 193-281). McGraw-Hill.

Bourdieu , P. (1977). *Outline of a theory of practice* (R. Nice, Trans.). Cambridge University Press .

Bourdieu , P. (1990). *The logic of practice* . Stanford University Press .

Bowlby , J. (1969). *Attachment and loss : Vol . 1. Attachment* . Basic Books .

Cherlin , AJ (2004). The deinstitutionalization of American marriage *Journal of Marriage and Family* , 66 (4), 848-861. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0022-2445.2004.00058.x>

Cialdini , RB, & Goldstein, NJ (2004). Social influence : Compliance and conformity . *Annual Review of Psychology* , 55 (1), 591-621. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.55.090902.142015>

Cialdini , RB, & Trost , MR (1998). Social influence : Social norms , conformity , and compliance . In DT Gilbert, ST Fiske, & G. Lindzey (Eds .), *The handbook of social psychology* (Vol . 2, pp . 151-192). McGraw-Hill.

Connell , RW (2002). *Gender . Polity* .

Connell , RW (2005). *Masculinities* (2nd ed.). University of California Press .

Durkheim, E. (1893). *The division of labor in society* (G. Simpson, Trans.). Free Press .

Eagly , AH, & Wood , W. (2012). Social role theory . In PAM Van Lange , AW Kruglanski , & ET Higgins (Eds .), *Handbook of theories of social psychology* (pp . 458-476). Sage Publications.

Finkel , EJ, Eastwick , PW, & Reis, HT (2015). Best practices in relationships science : The ideal standard model and its application to understanding romantic relationships . *Journal of Experimental Psychology : General*, 144 (1), 30-50.

Fletcher, GJO, & Simpson, JA (2000). Ideal standards in close relationships : A review of the empirical literature . *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* , 79 (6), 974-995. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.79.6.974>

- Giddens, A. (1992). *The transformation of intimacy : Sexuality , love , and eroticism in modern societies* . Stanford University Press .
- Goffman, E. (1959). *The presentation of self in everyday life* . Doubleday Anchor Books .
- Hatfield , E., & Rapson , RL (1993). *Love , sex , and intimacy : Their psychology , biology , and history* . HarperCollins College Publishers .
- Hazan, C., & Shaver , P. (1987). Romantic love conceptualized as an attachment process . *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* , 52 (3), 511-524. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.52.3.511>
- Hofstede , G. (1980). *Culture's consequences : International differences in work-related values* . Sage Publications.
- Kağıtçıbaşı, Ç. (2007). *Family , self, and human development across cultures : Theory and applications* . Lawrence Erlbaum Associates .
- Kalmijn , M. (1998). Intermarriage and Homogamy : Causes , patterns , trends . *Annual Review of Sociology* , 24 (1), 395-421. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.soc.24.1.395>
- Karakurt, G., & Silver, KE (2005). Türk çiftlerinde bağlanma stilleri ve romantic isimlerin. *Türk Psikiyatri Dergisi*, 16 (4), 223-236. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.52.5.509>
- McCrae , RR, & Costa , PT (1997). Personality trait structure as a human Universal . *American Psychologist* , 52 (5), 509-516. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.52.5.509>
- Miller, RS, & Perlman , D. (2009). *Intimate relationships* (5th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Özgür, E. (2015). Türkiye's romantic relations with individual freedom and family freedom: Challenges faced by young people. *Sosyoloji Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 22 (3), 134-

150. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429399399>

Schwartz, SH, & Bardi , A. (2001). Value hierarchies across cultures : Taking a similarities perspective . *Journal of Cross- Cultural Psychology* , 32 (3), 268-290.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022101032003002>

Sheriff , M. (1936). *The psychology of social norms* . Harper.

Thibaut , JW, & Kelley , HH (1959). *The social Psychology of groups* . Wiley .

Wood , W., & Eagly , AH (2012). Biosocial construction of sex differences and similarities in behavior . In MP Zanna & JM Olson (Eds .), *Advances in experimental social psychology* (Vol . 46, pp . 55-123). Academic Press.